

Estimation of sulfur in coal samples by a rapid combustion-iodometric titration method

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Abstract : The estimation of sulfur in coal by combustion followed by iodometric titration is discussed in the present study. The inherent advantage of this method is a rapid and accurate analysis of sulfur content in coal, when compared to the conventional techniques like the wet chemical method using Eschka mixture and followed by precipitation by BaCl₂ solution as barium sulfate and Eschka mixture method combined with Inductively Coupled Plasma Emission (ICP) Spectrometric analysis. The present work describes the use of a combustion-iodometric titration method in the subsequent sections of the paper. The method has been validated by measuring sulfur content in different certified reference materials and it was found that the values of sulfur measured by this method are in agreement with the certified values. The present method is also environment friendly due to avoidance of use of chromic oxide as the oxidant and perchloric acid as part of the absorption solution.

Keywords : Sulfur, combustion-iodometric titration, determination, coal.

Introduction

The determination of sulfur in coal has been discussed using different methods dealing with composition of sulfur ranging from 0.1 to 8 wt%. The advantages of different existing wet chemical methods have been discussed by different researchers¹⁻⁴. One of the common disadvantages is that they can be lengthy and require numerous manipulative steps, thus questioning the reliability of the method. Instrumental methods such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and the elemental analyzer require expensive specialized equipment adding to the cost of the analysis.

In this context, the present study focusses on the deployment of the modified version of the simple, inexpensive and reliable rapid combustion method of Finch and Ives⁵ designed for determining total sulfur in a wide range of materials containing 0.1–8 wt% sulfur for determination of the same in coal samples generated at Tata Steel, India. This work also finds reference to the method described in ASTM C 816-85⁶, which describes briefly the determination of total sulfur in graphite by combustion-iodometric titration method. This test method covers the determination of sulfur in coal in the concentration range

from 0.30% to 4.0% in a 0.10 to 0.2 g sample with a standard deviation of 0.15%.

In the present work, the sample mixed with iron chips and vanadium pentoxide is burned in oxygen and a major portion of the sulfur is converted to sulfur dioxide. The sulfur dioxide is passed through a potassium iodide-starch solution which is titrated with potassium iodate solution. The potassium iodate solution is standardized against samples of known sulfur content determined by the Eschka method as described in ASTM D 3177⁷. Sulfur in the coal can be analysed quickly with this method with good precision. It is also noteworthy that it is difficult to analyze sulfur in coal by combustion due to high volatile matters as volatile matters present in any substance tends to bleach the starch iodine complex. The present method takes care of the volatile matter by means of use of mixture of vanadium pentoxide and iron chips which accelerates the rate of conversion of sulfur into sulfur dioxide. This test method can also be used to characterize coal based on sulfur content. The present study discusses the application of this combustion-iodometric titration method in the subsequent sections of the paper.

Experimental

Required reagents :

Potassium iodate, concentrated hydrochloric acid, starch, potassium hydroxide, vanadium pentoxide, concentrated sulfuric acid and tin foil were procured from E. Merck, India. All reagents used in this work were AR/GR grades. Double distilled water confirming to Type II of ASTM D 1193-06⁸ was used in the preparation of the reagent solutions.

Preparation of reagent solutions :

N/32 potassium iodate solution : Dissolve 0.0444 g of potassium iodate (KIO₃) in water and dilute to 1 L. The sulfur equivalent for the KIO₃ solution is based on the following reactions :

(On the basis of 100% conversion of sulfur to SO₂, 1 mL of this solution is equivalent to 20 µg of sulfur)

Starch-potassium iodide solution : Add 2 g of arrow-root starch to 50 mL of water. Separately boil 150 mL of water and slowly add the starch solution with continuous stirring. Cool and add 6 g of potassium iodide (KI), and pour the resulting solution into a flask, which may be stored in a refrigerator.

30% KOH solution : Dissolve 30 g of KOH pellets in 50 mL distilled water and make up the volume to 100 mL in a volumetric flask.

Apparatus :

Fig. 1 represents a schematic flow diagram of the process, wherein a tubular furnace having a maximum temperature of about 1300 °C is used for the combustion activity. Refractory combustion boats of approximately 70 mm internal length (pre-ignited) at 1000 °C have been used in this process. The oxygen flow to the furnace is initially passed through a reagent bottle containing 30% KOH solution for removal of any carbon dioxide and then it is passed through a reagent bottle containing concentrated sulfuric acid for removal of any moisture. The KOH solution and sulfuric acid solution are separated by an empty reagent bottle to avoid any mixing up of these two solutions.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of the experimental setup.

Procedure :

Adjust the temperature of the furnace to 1200 °C. Turn on the oxygen and set the flow to 1 L/min. Fill the burette with iodate solution. Rinse the titration vessel with concentrated HCl solution and drain. Fill the SO₂ titration vessel with 8 mL concentrated HCl solution and add 200 mL of double distilled water. Add 2 mL of starch-KI solution to the titration vessel. Adjust the color of the solution in the titration vessel to a medium blue by additions of small amounts of KIO₃ solution. This colour will be the colour of the end point.

Remove the stopper from the mouth of the combustion tube. Take around 0.1–0.2 g of accurately weighed coal sample (depending on the sulfur content) on a tin foil spread over the refractory combustion boat and put around 0.30 g of vanadium pentoxide over the coal sample. Then, around 0.5–0.7 g iron chips is added and the boat is inserted into the tubular muffle furnace hot zone. Replace the stopper for sending the flow of oxygen gas through the combustion tube, so as to perform the ignition of the boat. During the combustion process, SO₂ gas is liberated and absorbed in the solution of the titration vessel. This solution is titrated with the KIO₃ solution to maintain the blue color developed as discussed in the previous paragraph. When the combustion of the sample is complete, record the volume of KIO₃ solution used for the titration. Make a blank run on an empty pre-fired boat, igniting for the same length of time as the sample.

Run standard sulfur samples (analyzed by Eschka method as described in ASTM D 3177⁷) in a similar manner to obtain a calibration factor. This is done whenever a new set of analysis is done. It may be noted that for all the experiments, the refractory combustion boats were pre-heated overnight at 1000 °C before being used for the experiments. The flow diagram of the process is given as Fig. 1.

Calculations :

Calculation of the sulfur factor :

The sulfur factor may be calculated as follows :

$$F = S/(R - B) \tag{3}$$

where, F = sulfur factor, S = amount of sulfur in the standard, %, R = amount of titrant for the standard, mL and B = amount of titrant for the blank, mL.

Table 1. Certified reference material : Coal samples-comparison between certified values and observed values

Sample ID	Certified value	Observed value	Difference in certified and observed value
LECO 502-443	1.12 ± 0.03	1.09	0.03
LECO 502-444	2.14 ± 0.05	2.09	0.05
SARM-19	1.49 ± 0.06	1.44	0.05

Table 2. Comparison of sulfur values obtained by combustion-iodometric titration method, gravimetric method and ICP analysis method

Sample ID	Observed values of sulfur (%)			Standard deviation
	Combustion-titration method	Gravimetric method	ICP method	
RS-384	0.64	0.68	0.610	0.035
RS-357	0.85	0.88	0.821	0.030
RS-342	0.92	0.96	1.036	0.059

Table 3. Repeatability and reproducibility data for different CRMs and samples by combustion-iodometric titration method

Sample description		Observed value of sulfur (%)					Standard deviation
Sample ID	Type	Run 1	Run 2	Run 3	Run 4	Run 5	
LECO 502-443	CRM	1.07	1.06	1.10	1.08	1.12	0.024
LECO 502-444	CRM	2.07	2.13	2.06	2.06	2.13	0.062
SARM-19	CRM	1.47	1.42	1.48	1.42	1.41	0.033
RS-384	Sample	0.66	0.66	0.60	0.66	0.64	0.026
RS-357	Sample	0.81	0.87	0.83	0.85	0.88	0.031
RS-342	Sample	0.94	0.88	0.89	0.96	0.92	0.034

Calculation of the amount of sulfur in the test sample :

$$\text{Sulfur, \%} = [(T - B) * F/G]*100 \tag{4}$$

where, T = amount of titrant for the sample, mL, B = amount of titrant for the blank, mL, F = sulfur factor, and G = amount of sample, g.

Results and discussion

The measurements were carried out by using the certified reference materials with different sulfur values and the results for the same are as given in Table 1. It was observed that the values of sulfur measured by this method are in agreement with the certified values of sulfur as shown in Table 1. The results were further validated and confirmed by comparing the results with gravimetric and also by ICP method for three different samples of coal which is represented in Table 2. From Table 2, it can be observed that there is a good agreement of values in case of measurement by all the three techniques, indicating the applicability of the combustion-iodometric titration method as compared to the other methods. Also, it was observed that repeatability and reproducibility tests indicate that the results are reproducible in nature which can be observed from the standard deviation between the values of five different runs for the different certified reference materials and test samples. Table 3 represents the repeatability and reproducibility data, which indicates that the proposed method is accurate and repeatable.

The most important feature of this method is the rapid determination of sulfur i.e. in about 10 min. Normally it is difficult to analyze sulfur in coal by combustion due to high volatile matter as volatile matter present in any substance tends to bleach the starch iodine complex. The present method takes care of the volatile matter by means of use of mixture of vanadium pentoxide and iron chips as the accelerators. Also, the use of chromic oxide as the

oxidant and perchloric acid in the absorption solution has been avoided, thus taking care of the health of the analyst. Thus, this test method can also be used to characterize coal based on sulfur content in an environment friendly manner.

Conclusion

The discussed method is a modified version of a rapid method for determination of sulfur in different coals as described by Finch and Ives⁵. One of the major benefits of the present method is that it is environment friendly due to avoidance of use of chromic oxide in the oxidant and perchloric acid as part of the absorption solution as described in the work of Finch and Ives⁵. The method was validated using different certified reference materials and it was found that the values of sulfur measured by this method are in agreement with the certified values.

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